

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Phytosomes: A Novel Vesicular System for Enhanced Bioavailability and Therapeutic Efficacy

Janhavi Gorane*, Kamlesh Mali

Department of pharmaceuticals, R.C. Patel Institute of Pharmacy, karvand naka, Shirpur. District Dhule pin code 425405(MS).

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 30 May 2025

Keywords:

Phytosomes,
phosphatidylcholine,
bioavailability,
phospholipids, antioxidants

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15553772

ABSTRACT

Phytosomes, a novel vesicular drug delivery system, have emerged as a promising approach to enhancing the bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy of poorly soluble phytochemicals. By forming stable lipid complexes, phytosomes improve solubility, absorption, and pharmacokinetic profiles, thereby overcoming the limitations of conventional herbal formulations. Recent advances have focused on optimizing phytosomes technology for various applications, including Hepato protection, neuroprotection, and cancer therapy. Patented technologies have introduced novel phytosomes-based formulations for targeted drug delivery and enhanced therapeutic outcomes. Despite their potential, regulatory challenges, scalability, and cost-related concerns hinder widespread commercialization. For phytosomes-based medicines to be incorporated into contemporary medicine, standardization of regulatory mechanisms and production procedures is essential. With an emphasis on recent patents and their uses in medicine, this study examines the pharmacological, structural, and mechanistic aspects of phytosomes. Phytosomes can help close the gap between contemporary pharmaceutical research and traditional herbal therapy by tackling formulation issues and regulatory barriers.

INTRODUCTION

For centuries, medicinal herbs and their bioactive components have been integral to the treatment of various diseases. Nonetheless, despite their therapeutic promise, several challenges impede

their clinical application. A significant factor contributing to the renewed interest in herbal medicines is the inadequacy of modern pharmaceuticals in effectively addressing all health conditions, coupled with concerns regarding the safety and side effects associated

*Corresponding Author: Janhavi Gorane

Address: Department of pharmaceuticals, R.C. Patel Institute of Pharmacy, karvand naka, Shirpur. District Dhule pin code 425405(MS).

Email ✉: janhavigorane@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

with synthetic drugs. Numerous studies suggest that compounds derived from plants frequently demonstrate superior efficacy with fewer adverse effects. However, their limited oral bioavailability presents a substantial barrier to clinical use like quercetin(1), thymoquinone (TQ)(2), piperine,(3) To mitigate these challenges, various formulation strategies have been proposed, including emulsions, liposomes, nano-formulations, molecular modifications, and prodrug administration. Among these strategies, phyto-phospholipid complexes, commonly referred to as phytosomes, have emerged as a promising method to enhance the absorption and bioavailability of herbal bioactives. The term "phytosome" is derived from "phyto" (meaning plant) and "some" (indicating a cell-like structure). Phytosomes, also known as herbosomes, represent advanced

vesicular drug delivery systems designed to improve the pharmacokinetic and pharmacological properties of poorly soluble phytoconstituents. They are created by complexing phospholipids with plant extracts or phytochemicals in an aprotic solvent, resulting in a stable and bioavailable formulation. In contrast to conventional herbal extracts, phytosomes demonstrate higher drug encapsulation efficiency, enhanced stability, and superior absorption due to the strong interactions between the polar heads of phospholipids and phytoconstituents. This interaction enhances solubility, leading to improved gastrointestinal uptake and augmented therapeutic effects.

Figure no 1: Difference between phytosomes and liposome

Structurally, phytosomes differ from liposomes. While liposomes encapsulate hydrophilic compounds within their aqueous core, phytosomes incorporate bioactive phytochemicals as integral components of their phospholipid structure through hydrogen bonding and polar interactions. This configuration enables phytosomes to effectively deliver both hydrophilic and lipophilic compounds, thereby overcoming solubility challenges. In the field of oncology, phytosomes

have garnered attention for their potential role in cancer therapy(4). Their capacity to evade the immune system facilitates passive targeting, while their nanoscale size and molecular weight (greater than 40 kDa) promote active targeting through the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect in tumor tissues. These mechanisms enhance drug bioavailability and site-specific delivery, thereby minimizing the systemic toxicity commonly associated with chemotherapy.

Originally developed for cosmetic applications, phytosomes have since been extensively investigated in the pharmaceutical domain. Research underscores their efficacy in anti-inflammatory(5), hepatoprotective(6), cardiovascular(7), and anticancer treatments(8). Their straightforward manufacturing process and robust chemical interactions ensure minimal degradation of bioactive compounds, establishing phytosomes as a reliable herbal drug delivery system. Given their improved bioavailability and therapeutic potential, phytosomes present a promising alternative to conventional cancer therapies. This review aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of their formulation, characterization, mechanisms of action, applications, and future prospects in cancer diagnosis and treatment.

Phytochemicals and Their Therapeutic Significance

Phytochemicals are naturally occurring bioactive compounds found in plants, known for their diverse pharmacological and nutritional benefits. These compounds contribute to a plant's color,

aroma, and flavor while also playing a protective role. Based on their structural characteristics, phytochemicals are broadly classified into three major categories: terpenoids(9), alkaloids(10), and polyphenolic compounds(11). Many phytochemicals exhibit poor water solubility, low permeability, and rapid metabolic degradation, leading to poor bioavailability. Factors such as high molecular weight, multiple ring structures, and poor lipid solubility restrict their absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. Additionally, enzymatic degradation and first-pass metabolism further reduce their systemic availability, limiting their therapeutic efficacy. These challenges necessitate the development of advanced drug delivery systems to enhance the pharmacokinetic profile of phytochemicals.

Structure of Phytosomes and mechanism of formulation

Phytosomes are plant extract-phospholipid complexes formed by binding individual components of an herbal extract to phosphatidylcholine, a lipid component of cell membranes.

Figure No. 2: Structure of Phytosomes

Phytosomes are vesicular drug delivery systems made out of plant extracts rich in active

phytoconstituents such as flavonoids(12), terpenoids(13), and glycosides(14). They are made

from phospholipids, usually phosphatidylcholine from soy or sunflower lecithin. They are structurally composed of a hydrophilic outer layer of phospholipid heads and a lipophilic inner core containing the plant extract. Phytosomes are typically spherical or vesicular in shape, with sizes ranging from 50 to 100 nm, which improves the bioavailability of herbal chemicals.

Mechanism of formulation

Figure no 3: Mechanism of formulation

Common preparation techniques of Phytosomes

Solvent evaporation method

The solvent evaporation approach for phytosomes production entails dissolving phospholipids and bioactive chemicals in an organic solvent such as chloroform or ethanol. The mixture is then subjected to rotary evaporation at low pressure to remove the solvent, resulting in the development of a thin lipid layer. This film is hydrated with an aqueous phase, then sonicated or homogenized to produce homogenous phytosomes. Utilizing the solvent evaporation method to increase bioavailability, silymarin-containing phytosomes demonstrated stability, a 133.53 nm vesicle size, and an entrapment efficiency of 97.17%. Spectroscopy and microscopy verified the successful formation of the complex and the integrity of the vesicles.(15)

Figure no 4: Solvent evaporation method

Anti-precipitation method

In order to prepare phytosomes using the antisolvent evaporation approach, bioactive substances and phospholipids must be dissolved in

an appropriate organic solvent, such as methanol, ethanol, or chloroform. In order to create a stable phytosomal complex, an antisolvent—usually water or a hydroalcoholic solution—is then progressively added to cause precipitation. After that, the organic solvent is removed, guaranteeing the phytosomes' better stability and appropriate encapsulation. The bioavailability and therapeutic effectiveness of poorly soluble bioactive

chemicals are improved by this technique. Utilizing the antisolvent precipitation method, *Murraya koenigii* phytosomes created to improve their antidiabetic qualities. When administered to diabetic Wistar rats, the optimized formulation (236 nm, 75.1% entrapment) dramatically decreased serum glucose levels, indicating better therapeutic efficacy than the crude extract.(16)

Figure no 5: Anti-precipitation method

Thin hydration method the typical thin-film hydration technique for making phytosomes entails dissolving bioactive substances and phospholipids in an organic solvent, such as methanol or chloroform. A thin film is created following solvent evaporation, and when it is hydrated with an aqueous phase, stable, nanoscale vesicles with improved bioavailability are produced. The thin-film hydration method was used to synthesize the enhanced pomegranate peel extract into nano-phytosomes, which had a one-year stability and a 58% encapsulation efficiency with a particle size of 154.0–216.5 nm. Resin column chromatography, which was previously optimized at a 3:1 resin-to-extract ratio, improved bioavailability and functioning by increasing

phenolic content 2.63 times with an 80.50% yield(17).

Lyophilization Method: Phospholipids and bioactive substances are dissolved in an organic solvent to form a lipid complex in the popular lyophilization procedure for phytosome production. After that, the combination is frozen and freeze-dried, producing a stable, dry powder with improved bioavailability and solubility freeze-drying technique were used to create NPDPs, innovative Naringenin-Loaded Dipalmitoyl phosphatidylcholine Phytosome for inhalation. In a rat model of acute lung injury, they showed excellent stability, pulmonary bioavailability, and anti-inflammatory properties,

making them a potentially effective clinical treatment.(18)

Figure no 6: Lyophilization Method

Characterization of phytosomes

Drug entrapment and loading capacity. The drug phytosomal complex was centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 90 minutes at 4°C to separate the phytosomes from the remaining drug. Ultraviolet spectroscopy can measure the concentration of free drugs. $EE \% = IP \div EP \times 100$, where IP is the initial phytochemical content and EP is the encapsulated phytochemical. Dialysis, ultracentrifugation, or Sephadex gel are used to eliminate free, unencapsulated phytochemicals. (19)

Particle size and zeta potential are important properties of complexes that are related to stability and reproducibility. In general, the average phospholipid complexes particle size ranged from 50 nm to 100 µm Zeta potential is measured using a variety of methods, such as Doppler velocimetry, micro electrophoresis, and DLS(Dynamic Light

Scattering)devices. Using the Doppler Effect in a laser beam, laser Doppler velocimetry evaluates the mobility of phytosomes. (20)

Structural and interaction studies:

X-ray diffraction is a useful technique for analyzing the microstructure of some amorphous and crystal materials. Active constituents or active constituent phyto-phospholipid complexes, PCs, and their physical combinations are typically the subjects of X-ray diffraction. A high crystal form is indicated by intense crystalline peaks in the X-ray diffraction of a physical mixture and an active ingredient. The absence of a crystalline peak in phyto-phospholipid complexes with active ingredients, on the other hand, indicates that the constituents in the complex with phospholipids have an amorphous or molecular form.(21)

Patented technologies in Phytosomes

Table no: 1 patented technologies in Phytosomes

Patent no	Phytochemical	Findings	Year
EP1844785	Olive fruit/leaf extracts	Enhanced bioavailability when formulated as phospholipid complexes.	(22)
WO2009/101551	Curcumin	Phospholipid complexes of curcumin provide higher systemic levels than uncomplexed curcumin.	(23)
US2007/0015698	Thymosin β -4	Formulation containing Thymosin β -4 for wound healing and skin treatment	(24)
US7691422	<i>Centella asiatica</i> triterpenes, <i>Vitis vinifera</i> extracts, <i>Ginkgo biloba</i> flavonoids	Oral compositions for cellulite treatment using these phytochemicals in free or complexed form with phospholipids.	(25)
EP1813280	<i>Ginkgo biloba</i> derivatives	Compositions for the treatment of asthmatic and allergic conditions	(26)
WO/2004/045541	Isoflavones	Soluble isoflavone compositions with improved solubility and texture characteristics	(19)
EP2228062 A1	Curcumin, piperine	Phospholipid-curcumin complex and piperine formulation for enhanced bioavailability.	(27)
EP283713	Saponins	Saponin-phospholipid phytosome complexes with improved properties.	(28)
KR102110510B1	<i>Centella asiatica</i> extracts	Phytosome comprising <i>Centella asiatica</i> extracts and the method of preparing thereof.	(29)
IN201721016683	Curcumin	Phytosome-based transdermal drug delivery system comprising curcumin for psoriasis treatment.	(13)
WO2019102346	Silybin	Phytosome formulations for enhanced bioavailability of silybin.	(30)
US11065456B2	Curcumin	Use of phytosomal curcumin in liver cancer treatment.	(8)
IN201811024990	Polyherbal formulation	Phytosome-based hepato-targeted synergistic polyherbal formulation for liver disorder treatment.	(31)

Marketed Phytosomal products

Table no :2 Marketed Phytosomal products

Product	Phytochemical	Findings	Year
Siliphos®	Silybin from <i>Silybum marianum</i>	Hepatoprotective and antioxidant properties	(32)
Ginseng Phytosome	Ginsenosides from <i>Panax ginseng</i>	Immunomodulatory effects.	(33)
Ginkgoselect® Phytosome	Flavonoids from <i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	Anti-aging effects and support for brain vascular health.	(34)
Oleselect™ Phytosome	Polyphenols from <i>Olea europaea</i>	Anti-inflammatory and antihyperlipidemic effects.	(35)
Polinacea™ Phytosome	Echinacosides from <i>Echinacea angustifolia</i>	Immunomodulatory properties and use as a nutraceutical	(36)
Greenselect®/ Green Tea Phytosome	Polyphenols from <i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Supports body weight balance and exhibits antioxidant activity	(37)
Leucoselect®/Grape Seed Phytosome	Polyphenols from <i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Cardiovascular support and antioxidant activities	(38)
Meriva®	Curcuminoids from <i>Curcuma longa</i>	Anti-inflammatory effects; supports joint health and healthy inflammatory response	(39)
Quercefit™ Phytosome	Quercetin	antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects	(40)

Conclusion and Future Perspectives

Drug delivery has advanced significantly with phytosomes, which solve the long-standing problem of many phytochemicals' low bioavailability. Phytosomes improve plant-derived bioactives' solubility, absorption, and therapeutic effectiveness by combining with phospholipids to create stable complexes. Their use in a variety of therapeutic domains, such as neurology, cardiology, cancer, and metabolic

disorders, demonstrates their adaptability in contemporary medicine. To fully realize their potential, however, future studies should concentrate on enhancing targeted delivery by ligand changes, using nanotechnology for improved stability and controlled release, and streamlining large-scale production processes to reduce expenses. In order to guarantee the safety, effectiveness, and market acceptance of phytosomal formulations globally, regulatory

standardization is also crucial. Personalized medicine has the potential to improve treatment results by customizing phytosomes according to genetic and metabolic profiles. Phytosomes are revolutionizing the role of herbal medicine in pharmaceutical development by providing a natural but cutting-edge scientific substitute for manufactured medications. They are very effective in cancer treatment because of their capacity to improve pharmacokinetics, which increases drug retention in tumor tissues, improves cardiovascular health by improving flavonoid absorption, and helps neuroprotective agents like curcumin and ginkgo biloba better penetrate the blood-brain barrier. Phytosomes also aid in the treatment of metabolic diseases including diabetes and obesity. They are also used in dermatology to improve the skin's absorption of anti-aging and antioxidant substances. The gap between conventional herbal therapy and contemporary drug delivery technologies will be closed as research into phytosomal technology advances and becomes more widely used in pharmaceuticals.

REFERENCES

1. Terao J. Factors modulating bioavailability of quercetin-related flavonoids and the consequences of their vascular function. *Biochem Pharmacol.* 2017;139:15–23.
2. Ballout F, Habli Z, Rahal ON, Fatfat M, Gali-Muhtasib H. Thymoquinone-based nanotechnology for cancer therapy: Promises and challenges. *Drug Discov Today.* 2018;23(5):1089–98.
3. Bi X, Yuan Z, Qu B, Zhou H, Liu Z, Xie Y. Piperine enhances the bioavailability of silybin via inhibition of efflux transporters BCRP and MRP2. *Phytomedicine.* 2019;54:98–108.
4. Gaikwad SS, Morade YY, Kothule AM, Kshirsagar SJ, Laddha UD, Salunkhe KS. Overview of phytosomes in treating cancer: Advancement, challenges, and future outlook. *Heliyon.* 2023;9(6).
5. Deleanu M, Toma L, Sanda GM, Barbălată T, Niculescu LŞ, Sima AV, وآخ. Formulation of phytosomes with extracts of ginger rhizomes and rosehips with improved bioavailability, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects in vivo. *Pharmaceutics.* 2023;15(4):1066.
6. Naik SR, Panda VS. Antioxidant and hepatoprotective effects of Ginkgo biloba phytosomes in carbon tetrachloride - induced liver injury in rodents. *Liver Int.* 2007;27(3):393 – 9.
7. Sarma H, Kashyap P, Zothantluanga JH, Devi R. Nanotherapeutics of phytoantioxidants for cardiovascular diseases. *Phytoantioxidants and Nanotherapeutics.* 2022;405–31.
8. Al-Rabia MW, Alhakamy NA, Rizg WY, Alghaith AF, Ahmed OAA, Fahmy UA. Boosting curcumin activity against human prostatic cancer PC3 cells by utilizing scorpion venom conjugated phytosomes as promising functionalized nanovesicles. *Drug Deliv.* 2022;29(1):807–20.
9. Atriya A, Majee C, Mazumder R, Choudhary AN, Salahuddin, Mazumder A, وآخ. Insight into the various approaches for the enhancement of bioavailability and pharmacological potency of terpenoids: a review. *Curr Pharm Biotechnol.* 2023;24(10):1228–44.
10. Pananchery J, Gadgoli C. Phytosomes of naphthoquinone enriched extract of root bark of *onosma echioides* exhibit wound healing activity in rats. *Indones J Pharm.* 2021;474–83.
11. Andishmand H, Yousefi M, Jafari N, Azadmard-Damirchi S, Homayouni-Rad A, Torbati M, وآخ. Designing and fabrication of colloidal nano-phytosomes with gamma-oryzanol and phosphatidylcholine for encapsulation and delivery of polyphenol-rich

- extract from pomegranate peel. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2024;256:128501.
12. Safta DA, Bogdan C, Moldovan ML. Vesicular nanocarriers for phytochemicals in wound care: preparation and characterization. *Pharmaceutics.* 2022;14(5):991.
 13. Alharbi WS, Almughem FA, Almeahmady AM, Jarallah SJ, Alsharif WK, Alzahrani NM, وآخ. Phytosomes as an emerging nanotechnology platform for the topical delivery of bioactive phytochemicals. *Pharmaceutics.* 2021;13(9):1475.
 14. Ercelen S, Bulkurcuoglu B, Oksuz M, Nalbantsoy A, Sarikahya NB. Development and Characterization of Plant - derived Aristatoside C and Davisianoside B Saponin - loaded Phytosomes with Suppressed Hemolytic Activity. *ChemistryOpen.* 2024;13(9):e202300254.
 15. Maryana W, Rahma A, Mudhakir D, Rachmawati H. Phytosome containing silymarin for oral administration: Formulation and physical evaluation. *J Biomimetics, Biomater Biomed Eng.* 2015;25:54–65.
 16. Rani A, Kumar S, Khar RK. *Murraya koenigii* extract loaded phytosomes prepared using antisolvent precipitation technique for improved antidiabetic and hypolipidemic activity. *Indian J Pharm Educ Res.* 2022;56:s326–38.
 17. Kazemi D, Ebrahimi SN, Kouchaksaraee RM. Fabrication and optimization of physicochemical properties of nano-phytosome from *Punica granatum L.* peel enriched polyphenol extract. *J Med Plants.* 2022;21(83):60–71.
 18. Yu Z, Liu X, Chen H, Zhu L. Naringenin-loaded dipalmitoylphosphatidylcholine phytosome dry powders for inhaled treatment of acute lung injury. *J Aerosol Med Pulm Drug Deliv.* 2020;33(4):194–204.
 19. Kumar A, Kumar B, Singh SK, Kaur B, Singh S. A review on phytosomes: Novel approach for herbal phytochemicals. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2017;10(10):41–7.
 20. Mazumder A, Dwivedi A, Du Preez JL, Du Plessis J. In vitro wound healing and cytotoxic effects of sinigrin–phytosome complex. *Int J Pharm.* 2016;498(1–2):283–93.
 21. Ghanbarzadeh B, Babazadeh A, Hamishehkar H. Nano-phytosome as a potential food-grade delivery system. *Food Biosci.* 2016;15:126–35.
 22. Chen RP, Chavda VP, Patel AB, Chen ZS. Phytochemical Delivery Through Transfersome (Phytosome): An Advanced Transdermal Drug Delivery for Complementary Medicines. *Front Pharmacol.* 2022;13:850862.
 23. Jadhav NR, Nadaf SJ, Lohar DA, Ghagare PS, Powar TA. Phytochemicals formulated as nanoparticles: inventions, recent patents and future prospects. *Recent Pat Drug Deliv Formul.* 2017;11(3):173–86.
 24. Gorain B, Pandey M, Leng NH, Yan CW, Nie KW, Kaur SJ, وآخ. Advanced drug delivery systems containing herbal components for wound healing. *Int J Pharm.* 2022;617:121617.
 25. Kalita B, Das MK, Sharma AK. Novel phytosome formulations in making herbal extracts more effective. *Res J Pharm Technol.* 2013;6(11):1295–301.
 26. Udupurkar P, Bhusnure O, Kamble S, Biyani K. Phyto-phospholipid complex vesicles for phytoconstituents and herbal extracts: A promising drug delivery system. *Int J Herb Med.* 2016;4(5):14–20.
 27. Di Pierro F, Settembre R. Safety and efficacy of an add-on therapy with curcumin phytosome and piperine and/or lipoic acid in subjects with a diagnosis of peripheral

- neuropathy treated with dexibuprofen. *J Pain Res.* 2013;497–503.
28. Semalty A, Semalty M, Rawat MSM, Franceschi F. Supramolecular phospholipids–polyphenolics interactions: The PHYTOSOME® strategy to improve the bioavailability of phytochemicals. *Fitoterapia.* 2010;81(5):306–14.
29. Singh S, Ushir Y V, Prajapati B. Phytosomes and herbosomes: a vesicular drug delivery system for improving the bioavailability of natural products. *في: Lipid-Based Drug Delivery Systems.* Jenny Stanford Publishing; 2023. 60–423 ص.
30. Awasthi R, Kulkarni GT, Pawar VK. Phytosomes: an approach to increase the bioavailability of plant extracts. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2011;3(2):1–3.
31. Singh RP, Parpani S, Narke R, Chavan R. Phytosome: Recent advance research for novel drug delivery system. *Asian J Pharm Res Dev.* 2014;15–29.
32. Selc M, Macova R, Babelova A. Novel strategies enhancing bioavailability and Therapeutical potential of Silibinin for treatment of liver disorders. *Drug Des Devel Ther.* 2024;4629–59.
33. Nuchuchua O, Inpan R, Srinuanchai W, Karinchai J, Pitchakarn P, Wongnoppavich A, وآخ. Phytosome supplements for delivering gymnema inodorum phytonutrients to prevent inflammation in macrophages and insulin resistance in adipocytes. *Foods.* 2023;12(11):2257.
34. Naik SR, Panda VS. Hepatoprotective effect of Ginkgoselect Phytosome® in rifampicin induced liver injurym in rats: Evidence of antioxidant activity. *Fitoterapia.* 2008;79(6):439–45.
35. Shakeri A, Sahebkar A. Opinion paper: phytosome: a fatty solution for efficient formulation of phytopharmaceuticals. *Recent Pat Drug Deliv Formul.* 2016;10(1):7–10.
36. Kumari R, Srikanth A. PHYTOSOMES: A NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM FOR POLY-PHENOLIC PHYTO-CONSTITUENTS. 2021;
37. Gilardini L, Pasqualinotto L, Di Pierro F, Risso P, Invitti C. Effects of Greenselect Phytosome® on weight maintenance after weight loss in obese women: A randomized placebo-controlled study. *BMC Complement Altern Med.* 2016;16:1–7.
38. Kidd PM. Bioavailability and activity of phytosome complexes from botanical polyphenols: the silymarin, curcumin, green tea, and grape seed extracts. *Altern Med Rev.* 2009;14(3):226–46.
39. Belcaro G, Hosoi M, Pellegrini L, Appendino G, Ippolito E, Ricci A, وآخ. A controlled study of a lecithinized delivery system of curcumin (Meriva®) to alleviate the adverse effects of cancer treatment. *Phyther Res.* 2014;28(3):444–50.
40. Riva A, Ronchi M, Petrangolini G, Bosisio S, Allegrini P. Improved Oral Absorption of Quercetin from Quercetin Phytosome®, a New Delivery System Based on Food Grade Lecithin. *Eur J Drug Metab Pharmacokinet* [انترنت]. 77–169:(2)44;2019. موجود في <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13318-018-0517-3>

HOW TO CITE: Janhavi Gorane*, Kamlesh Mali, Phytosomes: A Novel Vesicular System for Enhanced Bioavailability and Therapeutic Efficacy, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 5, 4936-4946. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15553772>

